

HOUSEHOLD GAS ACCOUNTING SYSTEM IN CALORIE UNITS

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The gas metering system in units of caloric value is considered. Information on the caloric value of gas is obtained from the gas supply company at the beginning of the accounting period based on the extrapolation of a mathematical model, the parameters of which are the caloric values measured during the year up to the moment of gas metering. Data exchange between the meter and the gas supply company's services is carried out using LoRa technology. Coverage of a given area of use is ensured by installing a set of regional gateways that support LoRa technology and transmit data to the digital networks of the gas supply company.

Keywords: gas caloric value, gas supply, measurement, system, structural diagram, LoRa technology, mathematical model.

Introduction. Recently, a unified indicator of its quantity has been used in the analysis of various processes related to energy consumption. Using this approach in the field of gas supply, the amount of gas provided to users also results in unified units in the form of calorific value. Calorific value of gas indicates the amount of energy it contains, which allows for a more accurate determination of energy consumption and simplifies the analysis of the efficiency of using a particular type of energy. This is especially useful for budget planning and cost control, since payment for different energy sources is reduced to the same units of measurement. In addition, calorific value measurement helps to better understand the environmental impact of gas use and contributes to resource conservation. This approach allows users to use gas more efficiently and reduce costs, providing comfort and warmth in their homes.

Natural gas extracted from underground deposits is actually a mixture of gases, the main components of which for gas and gas condensate deposits are methane and a small amount of ethane. However, its composition can vary depending on the place of extraction. In addition to methane and ethane, other hydrocarbons such as propane, butane, isobutane and other gases may be present in natural gas. The composition of natural gas affects its calorific properties. For example, gases with a high methane content can be used as an energy source for heating and cooking. Gases with a higher content of heavy hydrocarbons such as propane and butane can be used in industry or for the manufacture of gas fuel. Thus, the properties and uses of natural gas can vary significantly depending on its composition, which makes it important to analyze and control the quality of gas during extraction and transportation, as well as to develop specialized technologies for its use in various industries and the economy. Currently, there is a diversification of sources of natural gas supply to end users. Therefore, bringing the parameters of the gas mixture to the regulatory energy indicators requires determining the calorific value of the gas.

Analysis of recent publications. Despite all efforts in preparing a gas mixture of combustible gases to regulatory parameters suitable for use in everyday life,

the calorific properties of household gas are not stable. Increasing the accuracy of natural gas metering in units of calorific value requires constant measurement of this parameter and its inclusion in household gas meters.

Caloric content is measured by various methods [1,2]. Direct measurement of the caloric content of natural gas is carried out by the calorimetric method [3]. Often, the caloric content is determined by the component composition, which in turn is determined by gas chromatographs. Indirect measurements of the caloric content of gas by temperature, pressure, and the speed of ultrasound propagation in the gas medium are also used [4].

All these methods require complex equipment. Qualified personnel are involved in their use and maintenance. Therefore, determining the calorific value of gas cannot be carried out in random places and is not available to ordinary gas consumers.

Caloric content is determined by stationary equipment. In order to keep track of gas consumption in units of calories, the meter installed at the gas user must receive information about the caloric content [5].

Measuring the calorific value of a gas mixture and determining the amount of energy that can be obtained from this mixture uses stationary equipment such as a gas analyzer [6]. This information on the calorific value is necessary for accounting for gas in units of calories, since the calorific value of a gas can vary depending on its composition.

Purpose of the article. The purpose of the article is to develop a system for measuring domestic gas consumption in units of caloric value. Having received data on caloric value, the meter installed at the gas user can measure the amount of gas consumed and convert it to units of caloric value. This allows users to understand the amount of energy consumed in the form of a unified parameter to which the consumption of all types of domestic energy is reduced.

Presentation of the main material. Information on the calorific value of gas in each period of time is provided by the gas supply company. Given the autonomy of household gas meters, information exchange with them is possible using a wireless data transmission system.

Wireless data transmission in such conditions has certain features. The number of users is potentially equal to the number of gas meters. This is quite a lot. The amount of information is small and it can be transmitted monthly. The main limitation of the use of data transmission systems is the resource of the communication system's power supply cells, which is extremely limited. Household gas meters require maintenance or verification after 5-8 years, depending on the model and manufacturer. Reducing this service life will be perceived as a deterioration in the operational characteristics of the gas meter.

Thus, wireless communication systems that will be able to exchange information between meters installed at residential users and gas supply company services are required to ensure battery life, coverage area, and multiple access capabilities.

Among the well-known wireless communication systems that satisfy all the requirements for data exchange between the user's meter and the gas supply company's equipment is GSM technology. The mobile communication coverage area covers almost the entire territory of Ukraine. The possibility of multiple access to the gas supply company's services can be satisfied protocolically, using a series of communication attempts. One of the significant disadvantages of using GSM technology for data exchange is its short battery life. This parameter can also be improved somewhat using a protocol according to which the communication system is turned on only during a certain period of time. However, there are difficulties with power supplies, which have a long service life. Most of them cannot withstand high current loads. At the same time, at the time of initializing the connection with GSM base stations, GSM modems consume quite high currents. Therefore, in meters equipped with GSM modems, the power supplies must be periodically replaced between verifications.

A promising option for data exchange between the meter installed at the user and the gas supply company is the use of LoRa technology, which was developed to meet the communication needs of IoT (Internet of Things) devices. This technology involves the use of low-power digital data exchange systems in unlicensed frequency bands over a distance of several kilometers.

LoRa technology works by transmitting data using spread spectrum modulation (CSS) techniques. Compared to traditional narrowband modulation technology, this technology can achieve longer transmission distances and better immunity to interference. In CSS, the transmitted signal is spread over a wide frequency range, making it less susceptible to noise and interference.

Therefore, the main advantages of LoRa technology are low power consumption, long transmission distance, and strong anti-interference ability.

LoRa technology provides only the physical communication layer. Accordingly, data exchange can be implemented using its own exchange protocol, which will take into account the specifics of the system. Also, to ensure data transmission between the meter and the server of the gas supply company, you can use the well-known LoRaWAN protocol. Communication between

end devices and servers of gas supply companies is carried out through regional gateways between LoRa and the company's internal networks. Given the large coverage distance, the regional gateway should be located within a radius of several kilometers from the end nodes.

The LoRa gateway is located at the center of the LoRa star network. It is a multi-channel transceiver that acts as a data bridge between the terminal and the server. LoRa gateways are sometimes called LoRa base stations or LoRa hubs.

Although the definitions are different, they actually have the same meaning. The LoRa gateway uses different spreading factors, and the different spreading factors are orthogonal to each other, so theoretically multiple signals with different spreading factors can be demodulated in the same channel.

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Gateway throughput refers to the ability of a gateway to receive a certain number of data packets within a certain period of time. Theoretically, a single SX1301 chip has 8 channels and can receive up to 15 million data packets per day if it is fully compatible with the LoRaWAN protocol.

If the packet sending rate for a certain application is 1 packet per hour, a gateway composed of a single SX1301 chip can access 62500 terminal nodes. Of course, this is only a theoretical value, and the number of gateway access terminals is ultimately closely related to the number of gateway channels, terminal packet transmission rate, packet byte count, and expansion factor.

The number of nodes that a LoRa gateway can access depends on the channel resources that the LoRa gateway can provide and the channel resources occupied by a single LoRa terminal. If the LoRa gateway uses the Semtech reference design and the gateway uses the SX1301 chip, the number of channels is fixed: 8 uplink channels and 1 downlink channel.

The channel resource occupied by one LoRa terminal is equal to the time during which the terminal occupies the channel, which is closely related to the packet sending frequency of the terminal, the number of packet bytes, and the spreading factor of the LoRa terminal.

As the packet sending frequency and the number of bytes sent by the LoRa terminal increase, the time the terminal takes to send and receive the channel will increase, which will take up more channel resources.

When a LoRa terminal uses a higher spreading factor, the signal can be transmitted further, but the price is that it will take longer to transmit a single byte of information.

The LoRa terminal is an integral part of the LoRa network and is generally composed of LoRa modules and sensors. The LoRa terminal can be powered by batteries and can be remotely located. Each terminal that complies with the LoRaWAN protocol can directly

communicate with a gateway that complies with LoRaWAN, thus achieving interconnection.

The anti-interference ability depends on the characteristics of the LoRa technology itself and the design of the gateway. LoRa technology itself has ultra-high reception sensitivity and ultra-high signal-to-noise ratio.

LoRa technology, due to its properties, is widely used to create IoT devices. There are several companies and platforms that offer the creation of networks for data collection using IoT devices. These platforms offer equipment configured to deploy a wireless network of a given company. The advantages of such platforms are an already deployed network of gateways that support data transmission from terminals installed in the meter to data processing services. The disadvantage is that settlements are covered by a particular company's wireless networks to varying degrees.

The presence of a data transmission channel from the meter to the server allows you to receive a detailed

report on the user's gas usage. However, the information on the caloric content obtained in this way has a time delay. Gas, the caloric content of which was measured at the gas supply company, will reach the user after a certain indefinite time. In addition, gas is accounted for monthly, so the caloric content must be available before the start of its accounting period.

Monitoring the calorific value of gas over a long period of time allows building analytical models, the parameters of which are the results of measuring the calorific value of gas for the last period of time [7] and the given numerical values of mathematical models for each region of Ukraine. Greater accuracy of the model can be achieved by processing the values of calorific value measurements made for the previous period.

These models extrapolate the calorific value of gas for the next month. This value is transmitted to all users and used to calculate the gas consumed based on its calorific value.

The structural diagram of the domestic gas metering system in calorific value units is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structural diagram of a domestic gas metering system in calorific units using LoRa technology

The volumetric quantity of gas is measured by meters 1 in which modems 2 of LoRa technology are integrated. With the help of modems 2, wireless communication channels 8 are established with regional gateways 3. Regional gateways provide the possibility of wireless data exchange in a given territory. Territorial gateways 3 are connected to wired or wireless networks 9 of general purpose. In this case, the gas supply company is responsible for the operation of the wireless network of the territorial gateway, providing the equipment with the necessary power. Services of the gas supply company 4 are connected to the general purpose networks 9. Among the services provided by the services are information on the calorific value of gas obtained by extrapolating calculation by node 5, a general

information service for the user 6 and a service for accounting for consumed gas 7.

Conclusions. Based on the analysis of the requirements for the need to measure gas in energy units, a system for accounting for natural gas consumed in domestic conditions in calorie units was developed. It is proposed to use gas meters equipped with modems for wireless communication using LoRa technology. The proposed solution allows for monthly exchange of information between the domestic gas meter and the gas supply company services throughout the entire service life of the gas meter.

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